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POLICY BRIEF

01

GREENER FOR WHOM?

How Accessibility and
Amenities Proximity
Shape Inclusive
Urban Green Space in Cyprus

POLICY BRIEF 01

GREENER FOR WHOM?How Accessibility and Amenities Proximity
Shape Inclusive Urban Green Space in Cyprus

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Urban green spaces are increasingly recognised as vital contributors to the health, equity, and resilience of cities, offering significant benefits for well-being, climate adaptation, and social cohesion. In Nicosia, Cyprus, there is considerable potential to enhance the accessibility, distribution, and proximity of public green spaces. This Policy Brief, developed as part of the EU-funded TWIN2EXPAND project, draws on spatial analysis and stakeholder engagement to examine the 14 km Pedieos Linear Park and its new Strategic Masterplan for redevelopment, highlighting both the strengths and areas for improvement in current planning approaches. The planned upgrades—such as new entrances, facilities, and connections—represent an important step forward, but there is still untapped potential for the park to play a more central role in advancing urban health and resilience. Unlocking this potential calls for evidence-based strategies that align spatial justice, sustainable mobility, and inclusive design. By prioritising investments in underserved areas, embedding green spaces into walkable, transit-friendly networks, and designing with diverse users in mind, the Pedieos Linear Park can evolve into a leading example of equitable and accessible green infrastructure.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Urban green spaces are vital to the health, equity, and resilience of cities, offering multiple benefits for well-being, climate adaptation, and social cohesion. In Nicosia, Cyprus, where green infrastructure accounts for just 21% of the city's area, there is considerable potential to enhance the accessibility, distribution, and proximity of public green spaces and their amenities to better serve all residents. This Policy Brief, developed through the [TWIN2EXPAND](#) project, draws on spatial analysis and stakeholder engagement to examine the Pedieos Linear Park as a case study, highlighting both the strengths and limitations of current green space planning in Cyprus.

The 14 km-long Pedieos Linear Park, which extends across three municipalities in Nicosia, currently reaches around 19% of the city's population within a 15-minute walking radius. Yet, large high-density neighbourhoods around it remain underserved. A new [Strategic Masterplan](#) for the park introduces promising upgrades, such as additional entrances, improved connections, and expanded facilities, but leads to only modest improvements in overall accessibility. Furthermore, disparities persist in the distribution of on-site amenities and their proximity to surrounding communities. This significant urban green infrastructure holds great potential to improve urban health and resilience, yet remains underutilised, even with the planned enhancements.

To fully unlock the potential of urban green spaces in Cyprus, targeted policy action is needed. This brief proposes a strategy built on four key principles: **Proximity** (ensuring walkable access and equitable amenity distribution), **Diversity** (providing a range of functions and amenities), **Connectivity** (linking green areas through mobility networks), and **Stakeholder Engagement** (involving communities in planning, design and assessment of proposed developments).

This brief is intended to support policymakers, local authorities, and urban planners in making strategic, evidence-based decisions to ensure that green space access in Cyprus becomes truly equitable, inclusive, and accessible for all.

HIGHLIGHTS OF THE POLICY BRIEF

- [1] **Spatial Equity in Green Space Access.** Nicosia has only 21% total green infrastructure coverage, 2% urban green space and 4% urban tree cover, ranking lowest among 38 European capital cities for green infrastructure coverage, with major high-density neighbourhoods still underserved. **The Pedieos Linear Park currently reaches just 19% of residents within a 15-minute walk; planned upgrades raise this only to 20%.** Future investments should prioritise underserved areas for investment, guided by walkable proximity and spatial equity benchmarks.
- [2] **Diversity of Functions and Amenity Distribution.** The proposed Strategic Masterplan of the Pedieos River Linear Park increases on-site amenities by around 60%. **However, social, cultural, and animal-related amenities across the park remain unevenly distributed, particularly in the central sections.** Green spaces should provide diverse, inclusive functions, evenly distributed, to ensure the quality of green spaces and to support everyday use by all age groups and abilities, in all neighbourhoods.
- [3] **Sustainable and Inclusive Mobility Links.** Improved public transport frequency could increase park access from 20% to 31%, reaching over 80,000 residents. Shaded pedestrian and cycling corridors, barrier-free design, and transit-linked park entrances are essential for equitable, climate-conscious access.
- [4] **Participatory Planning and Collaborative Governance.** Engaging communities and local stakeholders local needs and preferences, clarified the impacts of proposed design interventions, and helped prioritise key issues and test alternative scenarios to inform future decision-making and improvements. Building on this foundation, green space planning should embed participatory processes at all stages, planning, design, and evaluation.
- [5] **Building on Evidence:** Ground decisions on an evidence-based approach based on geospatial analysis to monitor, evaluate and guide effective, equitable, and resilient urban greening interventions.

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INTRODUCTION

Urban green and blue spaces, such as parks, river corridors, tree-lined streets, and community gardens, are essential components of sustainable, inclusive, and climate-resilient cities [1]. They provide a wide range of critical services, from mitigating urban heat and improving public health to supporting biodiversity and fostering social cohesion. In Mediterranean cities like those in Cyprus, where rapid urbanisation, peri-urban sprawl, and rising temperatures pose growing risks, the need for equitable, accessible, and high-quality green infrastructure is more urgent than ever.

Despite increasing global and European recognition of green spaces as vital infrastructure, significant challenges remain. In Nicosia, Cyprus's capital and one of the least green capitals in Europe in terms of tree canopy and public green space, access to urban green is still uneven and insufficient [2], particularly in high-density and underserved neighbourhoods.

This Policy Brief draws on spatial analysis and stakeholder engagement conducted through the [TWIN2EXPAND](#) project. Using the Pedieos Linear Park, the longest urban green corridor in Nicosia, and the new [Strategic Masterplan](#) for its redevelopment as a case study, the brief examines how spatial analysis and participatory processes can be leveraged to strengthen green infrastructure planning and better serve urban residents.

While the park already offers essential ecological and social value, future interventions need to ensure that all residents, regardless of income, location, or ability, can access and benefit from such spaces. The brief identifies critical gaps and presents evidence-based recommendations for a more inclusive, accessible, and resilient approach to urban green space planning in Cyprus and comparable Mediterranean contexts.

Access to well-designed public spaces and urban nature is directly connected to improved quality of urban life, improved health, and decreased vulnerability towards climate change events. Furthermore, well-distributed and good-quality public spaces can be leveraged to build safer, more cohesive communities and stronger local economies. [1]

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[1] EEA. (2023). Who benefits from nature in European cities: A socio-demographic analysis (No. 2023/01). European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/who-benefits-from-nature-in>

[2] Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2022). Percentage of total green infrastructure, urban green space, and urban tree cover in the area of EEA38- capital cities (excluding Liechtenstein) [Data set]. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/percentage-of-total-green-infrastructure>

[3] Garau, P. (2015). Global public space toolkit: From global principles to local policies and practice. UNON Publishing Services Section. United Nations Human Settlements Programme.

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Urban green spaces are increasingly recognised as key contributors to sustainability in international frameworks and European policies, which provide a foundation for promoting more equitable, inclusive, and climate-resilient urban development through well-distributed and high-quality public green spaces. The **Global United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 11.7** explicitly aims to provide ‘universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces’ requiring that, by 2030, every city guarantees universal access to green public spaces, especially for women, children, older persons and people with disabilities (UN, 2015). The **New Urban Agenda** calls Member States to foster “safe, inclusive, accessible, green and quality public spaces” as multifunctional platforms for community interaction, health promotion, economic activity and cultural dialogue (Habitat III, 2016).

Underpinning these global commitments, the **UN-Habitat Global Public Space Programme** provides a practical toolkit for participatory design and stewardship of high-quality green spaces (UN-Habitat, 2015). The **World Health Organization** recommends 0.5–1 ha of green space per resident within a 300m walk for optimal health and social equity (WHO, 2016). **UCLG Global Charter-Agenda for Human Rights in the City** frames quality green public spaces as a fundamental right, urging cities to set measurable targets, guarantee participatory planning and report transparently on equitable access and maintenance (UCLG, 2012).

At the European level, policy frameworks translate global vision into binding action. The **European Green Deal** channels funding into expanding and upgrading urban environments and subsequently green spaces to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 (COM 2019/0640). The **Green Infrastructure Strategy** defines green infrastructure as a planned network of parks, street trees, green roofs and wetlands, mandating its integration into spatial plans and Cohesion programmes (COM 2013/0249). Building on this, the **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030** encourages bringing nature back into cities by creating biodiverse and accessible green infrastructure and compels every city with over 20 000 inhabitants to adopt Urban Greening Plans - Target 14 (COM 2020/0380) (EC, 2020).

At the national level, Cyprus strengthens its policy framework through key laws and strategies. The **Town and Country Planning Law** (Cap. 96 and amendments) mandates local planning authorities to designate “open spaces and recreation” in their local plans, formalizing urban parks as vital elements of city planning. Current planning regulations specify the concession of a percentage of land under development as public green space to be transferred to the municipality during planning permit

Figure 1: The chart depicts the percentage of total green infrastructure, green urban areas and tree cover of 37 capitals (EEA-38, excluding Liechtenstein) as a percentage of their respective surface area. Furthermore, it shows the averages for all cities included in the Urban Atlas 2018 dataset, as well as for the respective 37 capital cities.

Figure 2: The chart depicts the percentage of total green infrastructure, green urban areas and tree cover of 37 capitals (EEA-38, excluding Liechtenstein) as a percentage of their respective surface area. Furthermore, it shows the averages for all cities included in the Urban Atlas 2018 dataset, as well as for the respective 37 capital cities.

procedures [4]. At the same time, the **Cyprus's National Biodiversity Strategy & Action Plan** (2015–2020, updated 2020 with a 2030 roadmap) commits the country to mainstreaming biodiversity principles across town planning, transport, and infrastructure (LEX-FAOC214104).

As Cyprus strengthens its commitment to sustainable and inclusive urban green development, key challenges in bridging policy and practice persist, including:

1. Need for Alignment Across Multiple Authorities

Urban greening responsibilities are currently distributed across several institutions. Strategic land-use planning is led by the Department of Town Planning and Housing (Ministry of Interior); biodiversity objectives fall under the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment; while municipalities, varying in size and capacity, oversee the design and maintenance of local green spaces. Enhancing coordination among these actors is essential to ensure cohesive planning and delivery.

2. Gap in a Unified National Strategy and Local Urban Greening Plans

The absence of a dedicated national urban greening strategy and locally grounded Urban Greening Plans makes it challenging to guide long-term investments, safeguard green space locations, and establish common standards for quality, accessibility, and spatial equity across municipalities.

3. Uneven Distribution of Green Space Due to Historic Development Patterns

While current planning regulations require a percentage of land to be allocated for green space during development, past periods of rapid urbanisation, particularly during the 1980s, did not always follow this approach [5]. As a result, green space provision remains uneven across neighbourhoods, with some high-density areas underserved.

4. Need to Strengthen Local Capacity and Resources

Many municipalities face limitations in technical capacity, staffing, and financial resources to develop, implement, and maintain high-quality green infrastructure. Supporting local capacity will be vital to ensure green space planning is effective, inclusive, and sustainable over the long term.

The analysis of the Pedieos Linear Park addresses two research questions:

To what extent are urban green spaces, notably the Pedieos Linear Park, accessible to all residents?

How do crucial elements such as amenities proximity impact the usage and social inclusiveness of these vital spaces?

[4] Ministry of Interior, Department of Town Planning and Housing, Republic of Cyprus (2016), National Report, HABITAT III: Third United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development

[5] *ibid*

CASE STUDY: THE PEDIEOS LINEAR PARK, NICOSIA

In the Cypriot context and especially in Nicosia, urban green spaces are of critical importance, providing essential respite from the city's increasingly dense built environment and the escalating challenges posed by heat. In Cyprus, the median surface of accessible green urban areas is only 0.7 hectares, and 39% of the population lacks access to green spaces in their neighbourhood (Figure 2), the highest proportion among the listed European countries [6]. According to 2022 data from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Services (Figure 1), Nicosia ranks lowest among EEA-38 capital cities for green infrastructure coverage, with only 21% total green infrastructure, 2% urban green space, and just 4% urban tree cover [7].

The Pedieos Linear Park in Nicosia stands as a clear example of the significant urban benefits that green infrastructure can provide (Figures 4-6). The park stretches for 14 km (86 ha) along the riverbed, flowing through the adjacent municipalities of Nicosia, Strovolos and Lakatamia, and acting as a vital "green lung" for the capital.

A new [Masterplan for the Redevelopment of Pedieos River Linear Park](#) launched in October 2024, aims to strategically enhance its role as a truly inclusive and resilient urban green space, shaping the future of Nicosia's green infrastructure. Coordinated by DAEL (Nicosia Intercommunal Development Projects Company Ltd) and co-funded by the EU and the Republic of Cyprus, the plan aims to enhance the park's ecological and recreational value while fostering climate-resilient urban development.

By evaluating the new Masterplan's performance in terms of accessibility, equitable amenities distribution, and integration with the broader urban fabric, the research summarised in this brief aims to highlight both the strengths and limitations of current green infrastructure planning in Cyprus and to pinpoint critical policy and implementation gaps.

Figure 4: Nicosia Tree Coverage, Pedieos Linear Park is the Longest green coverage in Nicosia (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2022).

Figure 5 & 6: Photos from the Pedieos Linear Park, the Longest green coverage in Nicosia, photo credits: SURF Lab

[6] Poelman, H. (2018). A walk to the park? Assessing access to green areas in Europe's cities: Update using completed Copernicus Urban Atlas data (Regional and Urban Policy Working Paper No. 01/2018). European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/work/2018_01_green_urban_area.pdf

[7] Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2022). Percentage of total green infrastructure, urban green space, and urban tree cover in the area of EEA-38 capital cities (excluding Liechtenstein) [Data set]. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/percentage-of-total-green-infrastructure>

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed is multi-faceted, integrating spatial analysis with stakeholder workshops for the evaluation of the Strategic Masterplan for the Pedieos Linear Park. Spatial and accessibility analysis, specifically utilizing the **Space Syntax methodology** [8] via the **Place Syntax Tool** [9], provides a systematic understanding of spatial accessibility and connectivity within the urban fabric, objectively measuring ease of access and identifying bottlenecks.

The quantitative analysis was complemented by two iterative workshops that brought together academia, civil society organisations, residents, architects, business owners, and local authority representatives around the Pedieos Linear park to collaboratively a) prioritize needs and preferences and inform research questions, b) understand the impact of proposed interventions through the results of spatial analysis and b) evaluate alternative scenarios.

Across the two dedicated focus groups, participants collaborated into three thematic teams: Accessibility & Connectivity; Biodiversity & Green Infrastructure; and Public Space & Social Activities, highlighted key issues and developed key priorities. During the second workshop participants discussed the outcomes of the spatial analysis of the proposed master plan presented by the researchers, and proposed alternative scenarios that were again tested to facilitate the understanding of the impact of urban design and planning decisions (Figures 7, 8). The approach was based on the principles of **Structured Democratic Dialogue (SDD)** [10], a process for generating, documenting and prioritizing ideas in response to complex questions, fostering participatory decision-making.

[8] Space Syntax Methodology is a science-based & human-focused modelling approach to the planning & design of buildings & urban places. Includes a set of techniques for analysing spatial layouts and human activity patterns in buildings and urban areas, grounded on a set of theories linking space and society. (www.spacesyntax.online)

[9] Place Syntax Tool (PST) is an open-source plugin for space syntax and accessibility analysis in QGIS (available at www.smg.chalmers.se)

[10] Laouris, Y., & Romm, N. R. (2022). Structured dialogical design as a problem structuring method illustrated in a Re-invent democracy project. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 301(3), 1072–1087. doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2021.11.046

Figure 7 & 8 : Photos from the Second Stakeholders workshop, SURF Lab

KEY RESEARCH FINDINGS

Existing Situation:

The Pedieos Linear Park, is Nicosia's longest green public space and features **67 official entrance points** (Figure 9). Approximately **50,000 residents (19% of Nicosia's population)** currently live within a **15-minute walk (1200m)** of a park entrance, and **70 bus stops are located within a 5-minute walk (500m)** of these entrances. The park also provides **access to significant nearby infrastructure**, including 64 healthcare facilities, 43 educational institutions, 59 sports facilities, and 31 cultural venues. (Figure 15). **On-site amenities** currently include 32 Social facilities, 7 Animal facilities, 18 Essential Amenities, 11 Sports facilities, 5 Commercial facilities (Sport and commercial facilities proposed by the masterplan and mostly already implemented) (Figure 10).

Masterplan Impact on Accessibility:

The proposed masterplan aims to address accessibility challenges through **14 new pedestrian bridges** and **17 additional entrances (84 entrances)**, but its impact remains uneven.

Evidence from spatial analysis:

- 1. Marginal Population Increase:** The population within accessible range increases only marginally, from 19% to 20%, resulting in minimal improvements in overall accessibility to the linear park (Figure 11).
- 2. Densest Areas Left Behind:** The densest urban areas experience the smallest gains in park access, indicating that areas with the highest population density benefit least from these interventions (Figure 12).
- 3. Public Transport Potential:** Within a 500m walk from park proposed entrances there are 85 bus stops (+15). 80,797 residents (31 %) can take a bus from a stop within 200m of their home and then walk 500 m to reach the park. This highlights the immense potential of integrating public transit in park accessibility strategies (Figures 13-14).

Focus group:

- 1. Participants stressed the importance for stronger links to high-density neighbourhoods and transit hubs, along with the creation of green corridors that connect park entrances to surrounding neighbourhoods.** Given that extreme summer heat is a major deterrent, all approach routes should be shaded and planted, effectively extending the park's micro climate benefits into adjacent urban areas.
- 2. They called for universal access through inclusive mobility infrastructure, including uninterrupted pathways, clear way finding, adequate lighting, and emergency points to ensure safety and usability for all, including people with disabilities.**

Figure 9: Existing situation, Population reach from the 67 existing park entrances within 1200-meter walking distance

Figure 10: Existing situation, Accessibility to amenities in the linear park, within 1200-meter walking distance

Figure 11: Masterplan, Population reach from the 84 proposed (+17) park entrances within 1200-meter walking distance

Figure 12: Masterplan, Highest population density areas, show the least improvement in accessibility.

Figure 13: Masterplan, Bus stops that are within 500-meter walking from any of the 84 entrances

Figure 14: Masterplan, The population that can reach a bus stop within 200 meters and then access the park within 500 meters of another stop.

Masterplan Impact on Amenity Proximity and Distribution:

The masterplan proposes a wide range of new, additional on-site amenities organized into categories: 10 Social facilities, 25 Ecological facilities, 3 Cultural facilities, 8 Animal facilities, 11 Sports facilities, 5 Commercial facilities.

Evidence from spatial analysis:

1. Improved proximity to external amenities from the park. Within a 1200m walking distance from park entrances residents can expect to be able to reach 80 healthcare facilities (+33%), 56 educational institutions (+30%), 76 sports facilities (+29%), and 34 cultural venues (+10%) in the surrounding areas. (Figure 16)

2. Imbalances in on-site amenity distribution: Social, cultural, and animal-related amenities remain inadequately distributed, particularly in the underserved central section. High-density areas often benefit least from these new amenities, indicating a need for more precisely targeted interventions. (Figures 17-20)

3. Spatial disparities in amenity distribution. There are meaningful improvements in quantity, but spatial disparities in amenity distribution can still be improved, implying varying quality and variety of experiences depending on the area.

Focus Group

1. Participants emphasized the importance of strategically located rest areas including shaded seating, water stations, and accessible restrooms, to ensure comfort and usability for older adults, children, and people with disabilities.

2. They advocated for a dynamic public space activated through pop-up events, local festivals, and temporary cultural installations that foster inclusion, interaction, and community vibrancy.

3. Participants proposed a city-wide environmental education program rooted in the park, transforming Pedieos into a “living classroom” that engages schools across Nicosia and promotes ecological awareness from a young age.

4. They emphasized that a robust waste-management strategy is essential for improving both the visitor experience and habitat quality. Regular monitoring and clean-up of the river channel and stagnant side pools were deemed critical for restoring aquatic biodiversity and mitigating health risks.

In conclusion, the masterplan represents a solid step toward enhancing the Pedieos Linear Park’s accessibility and functionality. Further refinements are nevertheless necessary to maximize its impact and ensure its evolution into an equitable, well-connected, and ecologically vibrant urban green infrastructure for all Nicosia residents.

Figure 15: Existing situation, Accessibility to amenities from the linear park (from the 67 existing entrances)

Figure 16: Masterplan, Accessibility to amenities from the linear park (from the 84 proposed entrances)

Figure 17: Masterplan, Accessibility to amenities within the linear park - Social Facilities Distribution

Figure 18: Masterplan, Accessibility to amenities within the linear park - Ecological Facilities Distribution

Figure 19: Masterplan, Accessibility to amenities within the linear park - Cultural Facilities Distribution

Figure 20: Masterplan, Accessibility to amenities within the linear park - Animal Facilities Distribution

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The case study of the Pedieos Linear Park highlights key policy areas where targeted interventions can enhance the accessibility, quality, and social value of urban green public spaces in Cyprus. To unlock the full potential of green infrastructure for well-being, equity, and resilience, a multi-faceted approach is needed, one that addresses spatial distribution, connectivity, ecological and social inclusion, and institutional capacity for evidence-based design and planning.

[1] Foster Equity in Spatial Distribution and Quality

- **Prioritise investment in underserved areas:** Allocate resources to densely populated and marginalised neighbourhoods with limited access to green space.
- **Ensure consistent quality and standards:** Define strategic guidelines and minimum standards for green space distribution, design, and amenities to guarantee safe, well-equipped public spaces for all residents.
- **Establish measurable targets and equity benchmarks:** Set and monitor standards for proximity, amenity provision, and tree canopy coverage to guide planning and ensure transparency and accountability.

[2] Enhance Accessibility and Sustainable Connectivity

- **Integrate mobility and green infrastructure planning:** Ensure urban planning incorporates green space access into broader mobility networks, including shaded walking and cycling corridors linking parks to neighbourhoods and transit hubs.
- **Apply universal design principles:** All pathways and park connections should support barrier-free access for people with disabilities, older adults, and families with children.
- **Coordinate green space with public transport:** Align planning of parks with transit strategies by placing stops and nodes within safe, short walking distances of entrances.

[3] Promote Inclusive and Multifunctional Green Spaces

- **Require inclusive and multifunctional design:** Implement universal design standards to ensure green spaces support diverse uses and users. This includes accessible amenities such as restrooms, fountains, shaded seating, and inclusive play equipment.
- **Encourage community-led programming:** Support and incentivise temporary and recurring public uses—such as markets, cultural events, and educational workshops—that activate green spaces and foster social cohesion.

[4] Strengthen Institutional Capacity and Governance

- **Develop a national urban greening strategy:** Establish a comprehensive national policy with clear goals, targets, and investment pathways for green infrastructure, aligned with EU and global sustainability commitments.
- **Institutionalise transdisciplinary collaboration:** Formalise cooperation among municipalities, experts, and civil society throughout all phases of green space planning. Create participatory platforms that support co-creation and long-term community engagement.

[5] Ground Planning in Evidence, Not Assumptions

- **Adopt evidence-based design and planning:** All green space strategies should be informed by spatial analysis, demographic data, and participatory research. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation should guide implementation, track progress, and refine interventions.
- **Use spatial analysis and data to test and improve strategies:** Scenario testing and geospatial tools enable planners to simulate outcomes, adjust priorities, and make informed, resilient, and context-specific decisions from the outset.

CONCLUSIONS

The Pedieos Linear Park illustrates both the promise and the potential of urban green infrastructure in Cyprus. As one of Nicosia's most significant green corridors, it provides ecological, social, and health benefits, yet remains underutilised—particularly by residents in high-density and underserved areas. The proposed Strategic Masterplan introduces valuable improvements and also highlights opportunities to further strengthen spatial equity and accessibility through more integrated, inclusive, and evidence-informed planning approaches.

Realising the full potential of urban green spaces in Cyprus requires a shift toward holistic strategies that connect spatial justice, sustainable mobility, and inclusive design. This means prioritising investments in the areas of greatest need, linking parks through walkable and transit-accessible networks, and ensuring that all residents—regardless of income, ability, or location—can enjoy the benefits of high-quality green public space.

Achieving this vision depends on stronger institutional coordination and meaningful public engagement. Inclusive processes that incorporate community knowledge, supported by cross-sector collaboration and evidence-based design and planning, are essential for designing green spaces that are both resilient and socially responsive.

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ABOUT THE TWIN2EXPAND PROJECT

TWIN2EXPAND is a research project that aims to enhance the research excellence in the field of Evidence-Based Design and Planning (EBDP) at the University of Cyprus (UCY). The project seeks to address urban challenges and opportunities in Cyprus, which is a unique context for EBDP research due to its climate and history, while performing research and testing spatial models in diverse contexts. The project is coordinated by UCY and involves advanced partners from Europe with long-standing experience in EBDP: University College London (UCL), Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg, Politecnico di Torino (PoliTo) and Space Syntax Limited

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REFERENCES

Academic Sources

- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2022). Percentage of total green infrastructure, urban green space, and urban tree cover in the area of EEA-38 capital cities (excluding Liechtenstein) [Data set]. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/percentage-of-total-green-infrastructure>
- EEA. (2020). Healthy environments, healthy lives: How the environment influences health and well-being in Europe (No. 21/2020). European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/healthy-environment-healthy-lives>
- EEA. (2023). Who benefits from nature in European cities: A socio-demographic analysis (No. 01/2023). European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/who-benefits-from-nature-in>
- Larkin, A., & Hystad, P. (2019). Evaluating street tree effect on urban heat using mobile thermal imaging and in situ measurements. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 44, 126361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.02.012>
- Laouris, Y., & Romm, N. R. A. (2022). Structured dialogical design as a problem-structuring method illustrated in a re-invent democracy project. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 301(3), 1072–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2021.11.046>
- Nielsen, A. B., van den Bosch, M., Maruthaveeran, S., & van den Bosch, C. K. (2014). Species richness in urban parks and its drivers: A review of empirical evidence. *Urban Ecosystems*, 17, 305–327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-013-0316-1>
- Nutsford, D., Pearson, A. L., Kingham, S., & Reitsma, F. (2016). Residential exposure to visible blue space (but not green space) associated with lower psychological distress in a capital city. *Health & Place*, 39, 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2016.03.002>
- Poelman, H. (2018). A walk to the park? Assessing access to green areas in Europe's cities: Update using completed Copernicus Urban Atlas data (Regional and Urban Policy Working Paper 01/2018). European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/work/2018_01_green_urban_area.pdf
- Saraev, V. (2020). Economic benefits of urban green infrastructure: Evidence and challenges. *Forest Research*. <https://cdn.forestresearch.gov.uk/2022/02/nweeconomicbenefitsofgi-investigating.pdf>
- Toftager, M., Ekholm, O., Schipperijn, J., Stigsdotter, U. K., Petersen, J. H., & Randrup, T. B. (2011). Distance to green space and physical activity: A Danish national representative survey. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 8(6), 741–749. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.8.6.741>
- Ziter, C. D., Pedersen, E. J., Kucharik, C. J., & Turner, M. G. (2019). Scale-dependent interactions between tree canopy cover and impervious surfaces reduce daytime urban heat during summer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(15), 7575–7580. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1817561116>

Policies, Frameworks, and Toolkits

- European Commission. (2013). Green Infrastructure (GI) — Enhancing Europe's Natural Capital (COM/2013/0249 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52013DC0249>
- European Commission. (2019). The European Green Deal (COM/2019/640 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>
- European Commission. (2020). EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM/2020/380 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0380>
- European Commission. (2021). EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (COM/2021/82 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0082>
- European Union. (2024). Nature Restoration Law (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1991>
- UN-Habitat. (2015). Global public space toolkit: From global principles to local policies and practice. United Nations Human Settlements Programme. <https://unhabitat.org/global-public-space-toolkit>
- UN-Habitat. (2016). New Urban Agenda. Habitat III. <https://habitat3.org/the-new-urban-agenda/>
- United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG). (2012). Global Charter-Agenda for Human Rights in the City. <https://www.uclg-cisd.org/en/right-to-the-city/world-charter-agenda>
- United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11>
- United Nations Decade on Ecosystem Restoration. (2021–2030). <https://www.decadeonrestoration.org/>
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2016). Urban green spaces and health: A review of evidence. <https://www.euro.who.int/en/publications/abstracts/urban-green-spaces-and-health-a-review-of-evidence-2016>
- National Laws and Strategies (Cyprus)**
- Cyprus. (n.d.). Town and Country Planning Law, Cap. 96 (with amendments). https://www.cylaw.org/nomoi/enop/non-ind/0_96/full.html
- FAOLEX. (2020). Cyprus: National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan 2015–2020 (LEX-FAOC214104). <https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC214104/>

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